

AT THE MECHANISM OF GRAPHITE SPLITTING BOUBY AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS

Yurov V.M.,

Candidate of phys.-mat. sciences, associate professor
KarTU, Karaganda, Kazakhstan

Zhangozin K.N.

Candidate of Physics and Mathematics Sciences, Associate Professor,
TSK Vostok LLP, Ust-Kamenogorsk, Kazakhstan**Abstract**

A review of the methods of graphite by aqueous solutions is given. Of particular interest are experimental results indicating the intercalation of graphite microclaster water. A review of the structure of microclaster water is given. Our model is proposed by the splitting of graphite by aqueous solutions. When the graphite breakdown by aqueous solutions, cracks were not taken into account, which are formed in any solid body. We received a model of splitting graphite by aqueous solutions, using only experimental data.

Keywords: graphite, carbon, splitting, crack, water, solution, intercalation, model, atom.

Introduction

Graphite is one of the most stable of all existing forms of carbon [1] and the best known example of substances with a layered structure, in which layers formed by covalently bonded carbon atoms in sp^2 hybridization (with a binding energy of ≈ 524 kJ/mol) are connected by Van-forces. der-Waals (with binding energy ≈ 7 kJ/mol) [2]. In nature, the process of graphite formation can be divided into three main stages: the transformation of organic material into peat, then into coal, and finally into graphite [3]. The process of artificially forming graphite involves heating coal to very high temperatures in special graphitizing mixtures. These mixtures contain various additives that promote the transformation of coal into graphite. This process, known as graphitization, produces high-quality and uniform graphite used in many technical and scientific fields [4, 5]. By splitting graphite, we obtain monoatomic monolayers, otherwise known as graphene, which has unique physicochemical properties. To obtain graphene from graphite, there are several methods, a review of which is given in [6-8].

The purpose of this article is to propose a mechanism for the splitting of graphite by aqueous solutions in order to obtain graphene-like structures.

Method of splitting graphite with aqueous solutions

In pure water, graphite practically does not react. Its layered structure does not allow water molecules to penetrate between the layers of graphite. Therefore, graphite remains stable and does not dissolve [9]. However, if the water contains other chemical compounds such as acids or alkalis, then the graphite may be susceptible to corrosion [10]. Graphite can react with hydrogen, which is produced by the electrolysis of water, and form graphite, a single-layer carbon structure [11]. During the electrolysis of water, in addition to hydrogen, oxygen is formed, which leads to the formation of carbon oxides [12]. In [13], a laboratory technology for producing few-layer graphene particles in aqueous solutions, in the presence of surfactants and organic substances, was developed by direct exfoliation of natural graphite under the influence of ultrasound (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Results of a TEM study of graphene particles from an aqueous suspension (a) and from suspensions containing OD: FPAS (b), APAS (c), PVP (d), PEG (e), naphthalene (f), benzene (g)) after six hours of ultrasonic treatment [13].

It was concluded that the most promising, from the point of view of organizing mass production, is the process of producing graphene by liquid-phase exfoliation [13]. In [14], the values of the limiting sorption/swelling were obtained for the first time for 18 systems of graphite oxides (GO) (B-GO, H-GO-polar liquid, as well as for GO membranes) under various thermobaric conditions. When describing the swollen structures of graphite oxide, the concepts of thermodynamics of two-

component systems were successfully used for the first time. The change in interplanar distances is accompanied by a thermal effect, which was recorded by DSC (see Fig. 2A for the system with 1-octanol). Similar changes in interplanar distances are observed in the B-GO-octanol-1 and nonanol-1 systems from 27.8 to 23.3 Å for octanol-1 (see Fig. 2B, 2C) and from 26.2 to 30.6 Å for nonanol-1.

Figure 2.

A) DSC curve of the B-GO-octanol-1 system in an excess of polar liquid, where moctanol-1/mB-GO = 1.23; B) Dependence of the interplanar distance in the B-GO-octanol-1 system on temperature, (B) on pressure [14].

In [15], the possibility of intercalation of (BF₄)⁻ into highly oriented pyrolytic graphite in a supercritical electrolyte based on carbon dioxide, acetonitrile and tetrabutylammonium tetrafluoroborate was first shown. The synthesis of graphene and graphene-like materials is based on increasing the interplanar distance, weakening the van der Waals interaction forces between graphene layers, followed by delamination of graphite.

Electrochemical intercalation of graphite with the tetrafluoroborate anion in acetonitrile in the first step leads to an increase in the distance between the graphite layers from 3.35 Å to 5 ± 0.3 Å [16].

In [17], experimental results were obtained for the first time indicating the intercalation of graphite with microcluster water (MCW) in centrifugal (Fig. 3) and electric fields (Fig. 4) with the formation of graphene nanostructures.

Figure 3. SEM image of graphite with MCF after centrifugation [17].

Since no changes were observed in distilled water, the work [17] concluded that intercalation of “microclusters” occurs into the interlayer space of graphite,

causing its expansion from 3.44 Å to 6 Å and, with prolonged exposure, increasing this expansion in some places.

Figure 4. Vessels with graphite before exposure to an electric field. On the left is MKV, on the right is distilled (a); Vessels with graphite after exposure to a field of 500 V, 50 Hz, 80 minutes at 22 °C (b); On the left is a vessel with graphite in MCF, on the right in distilled water after an electric field at 30 °C (c) [17].

In Fig. 4b the same vessels after 80 minutes of exposure to an alternating electric field of 500 V (frequency 50 Hz). Room temperature 22 °C. It can be seen that the level of MAC has decreased (vessel on the left), and the volume of the decrease is comparable to the volume of graphite, which indicates that MAC has been introduced into a significant part of the interlayer space of graphite. It is visually observed that the graphite particles have swollen, which also confirms the fact that water is effectively introduced into the interlayer space. A repeated experiment, carried out at 30 °C, resulted in the graphite exfoliating, forming an abundant black foam that floated above the water (Fig. 4c). Since the density of graphene with a plate thickness of up to 4 nm is 40 g/liter, and with a thickness of up to 10 nm it is 260 g/liter, it can be assumed that the foam consists of graphene. Thus, a slight increase in temperature led to the fact that the swollen graphite began to delaminate with the removal of layers to the surface of the water.

Cluster structure of water

In 1993, Ken Jordan proposed his own versions of stable “water quanta”, which consist of 6 water molecules [18]. An interesting feature of this model is that it

automatically follows that freely growing water crystals, the well-known snowflakes, must have 6-ray symmetry. Subsequent experiments and ab initio calculations made it possible to find out more about the cluster structure of water [19-22]. In their opinion, the composition of water clusters consists of 3 to 50 water molecules each (Fig. 5). A review on the cluster structure of water was carried out in [23]. Heterogeneities of lower density water were identified as structures of tetrahedrally bound molecules (low-density clusters, LDC), and heterogeneities of higher density (high-density clusters, HDC) as clusters with broken hydrogen bonds. Bond disruptions in HDC increase with increasing temperature, while tetrahedral coordination in LDC remains unchanged, and their size decreases slightly.

The influence of dissolved atmospheric gases on the structure of water has practically not been studied, although it is apparently significant. This follows from the message that as it heats up from 20 to 40 °C (see Fig. 4c), the electrical conductivity of water experiences a series of jumps in narrow temperature ranges, some of which are associated with the presence of nitrogen, and some with the presence of oxygen.

Figure 5. Clusters in the structure of water [22].

A later work [24] states that water has a cluster structure over the entire temperature range from 0 to 100 °C. Estimates show that the bulk of water molecules (up to 99%) are located inside clusters. Clusters are solid structures. The binding energy of a water molecule with a cluster is ~ 3.5 times higher than the heat of melting of ice per molecule. The lifetime of a molecule in a cluster is significantly longer than the time of thermal vibrations of molecules in a solid.

The obtained results on the structure of water play an important role in the mechanism of metabolism in the human body. The cell is covered with a membrane. Water carries nutrients into the cell. It also participates in the removal of “waste” waste from the cell. For a long time it was believed that exchange occurs due to the diffusion of nutrients through the membrane into the cell and waste products out. The pore-forming protein aquaporin is part of the membrane. Let us compare the experimentally measured parameters of aquaporin pores with the properties of water. The average pore diameter is ~ 0.6 nm, the pore channel length is ~ 8 -10 nm. The size of a water cluster at a temperature of 36.6 °C, according to [24], exceeds the transverse size of the pore by ~ 8 times. Consequently, the exchange of the cell with the environment is determined only by free water molecules. The average free path of an H_2O molecule exceeds the transverse size of a cell membrane pore by 6 times. Consequently, there is a physical vacuum in the pore channel. At a temperature of 36.6 °C, the speed of a water molecule is 655 m/s. At this speed, the travel time of a water molecule along the pore channel in the membrane will be about $1.5 \cdot 10^{-11}$ s.

If the flux of H_2O molecules through the pore is equal to $3 \cdot 10^9$ 1/s, the average time interval between molecules will be $3.3 \cdot 10^{-10}$ s. Consequently, the time interval between water molecules is 22 times greater than the time of passage of a molecule through the pore channel in the membrane. Thus, 95% of the time, the aquaporin channel is empty and not only the process of nutrients entering the cell is possible, but also the reverse process - the removal of waste waste from the cell through the same channel. A comparison of the size of pores in cell membranes with the size of a water cluster shows that the exchange of substances through the pores is molecular in nature. The obtained data on a relatively small number of free molecules are in good agreement with data on the mechanisms of superplasticity of hydrogen-saturated titanium.

Two Patents (Lorenzen L.H.) more than 20 years ago described the process of producing microcluster water [25, 26]. First, the source water is boiled to produce steam. Next, the steam is passed through a magnetic field and the steam condenses at temperatures above 0 °C in the presence of light ranging from the far infrared to ultraviolet spectrum. At least one metasilicate salt stabilizer and food additive template are added to the condensed steam composition. The concentration of the food additive is 1% or less. Condensed steam is exposed to pressure greater than 1 atmosphere; and then release the pressure to produce microcluster water. Microcluster water produces a 170 NMR resonance signal at 115 Hz, has a conductivity of at least $3.7 \mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$, and has a surface tension of less than 61 dyne/cm.

Dr. Hidemitsu Hayashi [27] published a paper against the cluster structure of water in February 2023.

The most commonly used evidence is nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) results [25, 26]. The idea is that the wider its band, the larger the water cluster. As can be seen in Fig. 6, ionized water has a smaller bandwidth.

At first glance, this looks quite convincing. However, the problem is that the band width depends on pH [27], and not on cluster size. Any deviation from neutral pH in any direction will lead to a similar result [27].

Figure 6. NMR of ionized and ordinary water [27].

Dr. Hidemitsu Hayashi argues that until now, from a physical and chemical point of view, there has been no convincing evidence for the existence of stable microclusters of water, and research in this field has consistently refuted this claim, which is not surprising since this claim contradicts the basic and fundamental principles of chemistry.

Our model of graphite splitting with aqueous solutions

When splitting graphite with aqueous solutions, cracks that form in any solid [28], obtained by any method in nature or artificially, were not taken into account [29, 30]. This is due to the presence of a surface on a solid body and an associated surface layer, the thickness of which is 2-6 nm [31, 32] and differs from

the properties of the rest of the volume. In this case, the surface layer is characterized by anisotropy [33].

The thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ and the length of nanocracks L_{nm} are given by us by the empirical formula [28, 31-33]:

$$R(I) = L_{nm} = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \alpha \cdot \nu [M]. \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), you need to know one parameter - the molar volume of the element, which is equal to $\nu = M/\rho$ (M is the molar mass, ρ is its density), $\alpha = 1 \text{ m}^{-2}$ - a constant, so that the dimension ($R(I) = [m]$). Using formula (1), we calculate $R(I) = L_{nm}$ (Table 1) for graphite parallel to the plane $x = a = b$ and perpendicular to this plane $x = c$.

Table 1.

Parameters $R(I) = L_{nm}$ of graphite.					
Graphite	Structure	M, g/mol	$\rho, \text{g/sm}^3$	$R(I)_a = L_{nma}, \text{nm}$	$R(I)_c = L_{nmc}, \text{nm}$
C	C6/mmc-D ⁴ _{6h}	12,0107	2,26	0.90 (3)	2.46 (3)
			1,75	1.17 (4)	3.19 (4)
			1,65	1.24 (5)	3.39 (5)

From the table Figure 1 shows that the thickness of the layer $R(I)_a$ (and the length of nanocracks L_{nma}) varies from 0.9 to 1.24 nm in the upper plane, and the thickness of the layer $R(I)_c$ (and the length of nanocracks L_{nmc}) varies from 2.46 to 3.39 nm perpendicular to this plane. This is due to changes in the density of graphite and its layered structure. In table 1 number in brackets represents the number of layers - $n = R(I)/a$ (a is the crystal lattice constant). It can be seen that the number of layers of graphite is 3-5. We will call the layer $R(I)$ the surface layer and denote the surface energy of this layer by γ_1 . It was shown in [34] that the surface energy of a bulk metal γ_2 , with an accuracy of 3%, is equal to:

$$\gamma_2 = 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m [J/m^2], \quad (2)$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of the metal (K).

In the $R(I)$ layer, it is necessary to take into account the size effect and the surface energy of the $R(I)$ layer becomes equal to γ_1 [28]:

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2(1 - R(I)/R(I) + h) \approx 0,3\gamma_2, \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) shows that the surface energy of the $R(I)$ layer is three times less than the surface energy of the main crystal. To separate the $R(I)$ layer from the rest of the crystal, it is necessary to expend energy, which is called adhesion energy [35]:

$$W_a = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \approx \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 = 1.3\gamma_2, \quad (4)$$

where γ_{12} is the surface energy at the phase interface, which is negligible due to a second-order phase

transition. We calculate the internal voltages σ_{is} between phases γ_1 and γ_2 according to [35]:

$$\sigma_{is} = \sqrt{W_a \cdot E / R(I)}, \quad (5)$$

where E is Young's modulus of elasticity. Using equations (1) – (5), we calculate the elastic parameters for graphite.

Table 2.

Elastic parameters of graphite						
Graphite	$W_{aa}, J/m^2$	$W_{ac}, J/m^2$	σ_{isa}, MPa	σ_{isc}, MPa	E_a, GPa	E_c, GPa
C ($\rho = 2,26$)	3,613	1,323	5740	1370	7,59	3,48
C ($\rho = 1,75$)	2,801	1,026	3750	930	5,88	2,70
C ($\rho = 1,65$)	2,637	0,966	3440	870	5,55	2,55

For graphite, the average value is $T_m = 3970$ K and $\gamma_2 = 2.779$ J/m² (see formula (2)). According to work [1], graphite with a density $\rho = 1.75$ g/cm³ refers to pressed samples, and with a density $\rho = 1.65$ g/cm³ refers to pressed samples. Because of this, their mechanical properties differ both in the longitudinal (for example, Young's modulus $E = E_a$) and in the transverse directions ($E = E_c$) (Table 2). The Young's modulus of graphite is $10 \div 100$ times less than that of most metals.

The critical length of cracks in graphite should be determined according to [28]:

$$L_C = 10^4 \cdot L_{nm} = 0.17 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot \nu = 0.17 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot M / \rho \quad (6)$$

Let's calculate the crack length L_{nm} , $L_{\mu m}$, L_C for graphite.

Table 5.

Length of graphite cracks.						
Graphite	L_{nma}, nm	L_{nmc}, nm	$L_{\mu ma}, nm$	$L_{\mu mc}, nm$	L_{Ca}, nm	L_{Cc}, nm
C	0.90	2.46	90	246	9000	24600
	1.17	3.19	117	319	11700	31900
	1.24	3.39	124	339	12400	33900

Cracks L_{nm} , $L_{\mu m}$, L_C for graphite are due to their dislocation interaction [36]. The critical disclosure in the top of the crack for L_{Ca} is 6.1 nm, and for L_{Cc} it is 9.7 nm.

Consider the model of the traffic flow of the aqueous solution through the graphite placed in a cylindrical cup in a centrifugal or ultrasound field. Aqueous solution with the density $\rho(r, z, t)$, which moves by the dependence of $\beta(t)$ in the cylinder with the corresponding coordinate system, can be described by the diffusion equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho(r, z, t)}{\partial t} = D \left[\frac{\partial^2 \rho(r, z, t)}{\partial z^2} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial \rho(r, z, t)}{\partial r} \right) \right], \quad (7)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient of the solution.

The conditions at the border and the initial condition we will choose in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(r, z, t) \Big|_{t=0} &= \varphi(r, z), \\ \rho(r, z, t) \Big|_{r=R} &= \gamma(z, t), \\ \rho(r, z, t) \Big|_{z=0} &= \gamma_1(r, t), \\ \rho(r, z, t) \Big|_{z=\beta(t)} &= \gamma_2(r, t), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The task (7)- (8) is mathematically similar to our task [37, 38]. Solving it in a similar way, taking into account some parts that we omit, we will finally get:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(r, z, t) = J_0 \left(\frac{2r}{R} \right) e^{-a^2 t} & \left\{ \frac{e^2 J_0 \left(\frac{2r}{R} \right)}{16a^3} \ln t + \frac{L J_1 \left(\frac{2r}{R} \right)}{16a^3} e^{-a^2 t} \ln(t-1) + \right. \\ & \left. + \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} \right) \left(\frac{a^2}{z\pi} + \frac{a^3}{\pi^2 z \beta(t)} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} \right) \frac{2a}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{[z - \beta(t)]} \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

(9)

If time T is very large, then we will get:

$$\rho(r, z, t) = \frac{D^{3/2}}{\pi^2} J_0 \left(\frac{2r}{R} \right) \cdot \frac{t}{z \beta(t)}, \quad (10)$$

We denote $z = \nu t$, where ν is the speed of stream, t is the time of its movement. The movement of the phase section will take as a car model $\beta(t) = \beta_0 t$. We will use the asymptotic representation of the functions of the Bessel [39], then we finally get it with $r = R$:

$$\rho(r, z, t) = \frac{D^{3/2}}{\pi^{5/2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\nu \cdot \beta_0 \cdot t}, \quad (11)$$

Above is $\nu(z, t)$ the velocity of the solution at point z at the time t. Assuming that $\nu(z, t)$ depends only on the density ρ , we have that when the crack is empty ($\rho = 0$), the solution moves at a maximum speed $\nu = \nu_{max}$. When filling the crack, the speed drops to a complete stop ($\nu = 0$), when $\rho = \rho_{max}$. It will look like this mathematically:

$$\rho = \rho_{max} \left(1 - \frac{\nu}{\nu_{max}} \right), \quad 0 \leq \nu \leq \nu_{max}. \quad (12)$$

Relations (11) and (12) are shown in Fig. 7. From the formula (11), a significant dependence of the density of the solution flow on the diffusion coefficient is visible, i.e. From its rheology, which is equal, according to the classical theory of Newton [40], $D = \nu$, where ν is the kinematic coefficient of viscosity. We will consider the question of the viscosity of the solution from the perspective of the thermodynamic approach, which we developed in the work [41].

Figure 7.

Dependence of the flow density on the speed of the solution (a), the dependence of the flow density on time (b).

As a response function in [41], we take the kinematic viscosity ν , then we will have:

$$\nu = \frac{kT}{c} \cdot \frac{W}{G^0} \cdot \bar{N}, \quad (13)$$

where $NkT = PV = (V = 1) = P$ is the pressure in the flow of the solution; W is the kinetic energy of particles (molecules) of the solution $W = m V^2/2$; G^0 - energy of the mixture (solution); $C = \text{const}$, m is a mass of particles, v is their speed. Equation (13) will take the form (Fig. 8a):

$$\nu = \frac{1}{c} \cdot \frac{P}{2G^0} \cdot mV^2. \quad (14)$$

Considering that $G^0 = \gamma S$, S is the area, we obtain the following equation of the bond of the viscosity of the solution with its surface tension γ (Fig. 8b):

$$\nu = \frac{J}{\gamma}, \quad (15)$$

where J is a constant fluid under thermodynamic conditions.

The equation (15) is also true for graphite, according to which the flow of the solution is proportional to the surface energy of the graphite $\gamma = W_a/2$, where W_a is the energy of the adhesion of graphite.

Figure 8.

Theoretical dependences of kinematic viscosity on pressure for some liquids (a), illustration of formula (15).

We rewrite the formula (11), given the formula (1), in the form:

$$W_p = \cdot 10^3 \cdot \left(\frac{L_C}{M \cdot v \cdot t} \right)^{3/2}. \quad (16)$$

Here for aqueous solutions $J = 2 \cdot 10^{-8}$, $\beta_0 = 0.2$.

In the formula (16), all parameters on the right side are determined experimentally and give the value of W_p . If the value of $W_p > W_{ac}$ (Table 2), then the graphite is split.

Conclusions and offers

A review of the methods of graphite by aqueous solutions was shown by the absence of theoretical models of the specified process. The overview of the cluster structure of water showed on supporters and opponents of this approach. We received a model of splitting

graphite by aqueous solutions, using only experimental data.

Offers:

To obtain the equation, the splitting of graphite by aqueous solutions, you can use the theory of disasters with suitable control parameters.

Gratitude

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